

Mach-Zehnder interferometers that include electrochromic molecules to control the detection of single photons

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Abstract

One particularly fruitful research in the fields of integrated photonics, carried out by a good number of physicists and engineers, concerns the study of different types of materials to be used to control the detection of photons, if not just single photons, in interferometers. In a Mach-Zehnder interferometer, which consists of two beam-splitters, two mirrors and two detectors, a material that can cause a controlled change in the phase of light in one of the two arms of the interferometer consequently allows a control of the probability of detection at the two detectors. In this work, we use an electrochromic molecule, N,N'-bis(cysteine)pyromellitic diimide (BCPD), that has a refractive index dependent on the applied electric field. We simulate the single-photon detection probability at a Mach-Zehnder interferometer with direct light transmission and a waveguide-based Mach-Zehnder interferometer, consisting of two 3-dB couplers connected by two single-mode optical channel waveguides. With the employment of the nonequilibrium Green's function formalism, we have simulated the conductance of BCPD. The results could be of interest in quantum communication.

Keywords: Mach-Zehnder interferometer; electrochromic molecule; Hueckel theory; modulator; quantum information.

Introduction

Electrochromic molecules are materials that can reversibly change their optical properties, such as color or transparency, through redox reactions triggered by an external electrical potential. This phenomenon, known as electrochromism, has attracted great interest due to its potential applications in energy-efficient smart windows, displays, wearable electronics and multifunctional energy storage devices [1–3]. Among the electrochromic molecules, viologens are the most intensely studied species [4,5]. Other noteworthy electrochromic molecules are graphene molecules [6]. Moreover, the small molecule N,N'-bis(cysteine)pyromellitic diimide (BCPD) is a good example of short molecule that exhibits a distinct and reversible color change [5,7–9].

The color change, which is related to a change of the complex refractive index of the material, can be also exploited as a phase shift component in a Mach-Zehnder interferometer [10]. Mach-Zehnder interferometers with photochromic molecule or polymer, and with vanadium dioxide exploiting its insulating to metallic phase change, have been reported [11,12]. Mach-Zehnder interferometers that are based on direct transmission of light are composed of a light source, two beam splitters and two mirrors, and two detectors [10]. Mach-Zehnder

interferometers that are based on channel waveguides, e.g., in a glass slide, are composed of a light source, two 3 dB couplers, that have the same function of the two beam splitters, and two detectors [13,14].

We employ herein an electrochromic molecule, namely N,N'-bis(cysteine)pyromellitic diimide (BCPD) [7,8,5], as material in both arms of a Mach-Zehnder interferometer in direct transmission of light, and in a Mach-Zehnder interferometer made of channel waveguides, e.g., buried in a glass slab. We simulate the application of the electric field on BCPD via the addition of an electron charge to the molecule, with a subsequent change of its complex refractive index. The electric field induced change of BCPD refractive index in one of the arms of the interferometers allows a control of the photon detection in the two detectors of the apparatus. Moreover, by using the nonequilibrium Green's function formalism, we have found the conductance of the BCPD.

Methods

To study the optical response of BCPD, we have employed the Hueckel theory. The Hueckel theory is an established molecular orbital theory in which the molecular orbitals are written as linear combination of atomic orbitals, in which nuclei positions are fixed, and in which the molecular orbitals are linear combinations of carbon p_z orbitals (also other elements can be considered), neglecting electron-electron interactions [15]. In Equation 1 the time-independent Schrödinger equation is reported:

$$H\psi = E\psi \quad (1)$$

In this study, the Hulis package [16] has been employed to determine the Hamiltonian for BCPD (neutral and charged). Then, eigenvalues and eigenvectors have been calculated. To find the transition probabilities, we have employed the Fermi golden rule that is reported in Equation 2:

$$\Gamma_{i \rightarrow j} = \frac{2\pi}{\hbar} |\langle \psi^j | H | \psi^i \rangle|^2 \quad (2)$$

In Equation 2, the transition probabilities have been determined between the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and the unoccupied orbitals. The simulated absorption spectra have been built with a set of Gaussian peaks, with a linewidth c of the peaks of 0.1 eV. Considering the transitions from the ground state i th to the different j th excited states, the absorption coefficient can be written as in Equation 3:

$$\alpha(E) = \sum_j \Gamma_{i \rightarrow j} \exp\left(\frac{(E - (E_j - E_i))^2}{2c^2}\right) \quad (3)$$

With Equation 4, modifying the one reported in [17], the imaginary part of the complex refractive index can be extracted from the absorption coefficient:

$$k(E) = \frac{A\alpha(E)}{4\pi} \quad (4)$$

In Equation 4 A is a parameter (its value is 1×10^{15}). The real part of the complex refractive index can be derived via the Kramers-Kronig relations [18] (Equation 5):

$$n(\bar{\nu}) - 1 = \frac{2}{\pi} \mathcal{P} \int_0^\infty \frac{\omega k(\omega)}{\omega^2 - \bar{\nu}^2} d\omega \quad (5)$$

The Kramers-Kronig relations are actually Hilbert transforms as in the formalism reported in Ref. [19]. For the real part of the refractive index a constant offset of 1.5 has been used as done in Refs. [20,21]. Thus, it is possible to describe, via the employment of Equation 6, the complex refractive index of BCPD in the neutral (n_n) and charged (n_c) forms:

$$n_{n,c}^{complex}(E) = n_{n,c}(E) + ik_{n,c}(E) \quad (6)$$

For the calculation of the elastic transmission, the nonequilibrium Green's function formalism has been employed, following Solomon et al. [22]. Assuming that only a single site of the molecule couples to each electrode, for BCPD, the vector for the left electrode is given by Equation 7:

$$V_L = [\gamma \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0] \quad (7)$$

While the vector for the right electrode is given by Equation 8:

$$V_R = [0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ \gamma \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0] \quad (8)$$

Following the sketch of BCPD in Figure 1, the nonzero element of V_L is the first one, representing the connection between the nitrogen atom indexed "1" of BCPD and the electrode (that is going to replace the hydrogen atom). Similarly, the nonzero element of V_R is the eleventh one, representing the connection between the nitrogen atom indexed "11" of BCPD and the electrode (this electrode also replaces the hydrogen atom next to the nitrogen atom). The value of γ is -1 eV, as reported in Solomon et al. [22]. The broadening function is given by Equation 9:

$$\Gamma^{L(R)} = 2\pi\rho V_{L(R)} V_{L(R)}^\dagger \quad (9)$$

Where ρ is the density of state of the electrode, set to $1/2\pi$ (eV)⁻¹ (as in Solomon et al. [22]). With the broadening function, the tunneling self-energy, which is purely imaginary value, can be determined as in Equation 10

$$\Sigma_T^{L(R)} = -\frac{i}{2} \Gamma^{L(R)} \quad (10)$$

In Equation 11, the energy dependent retarded Green's function is given by

$$G^r(E) = (E - H_{mol} - \Sigma_T^L - \Sigma_T^R)^{-1} \quad (11)$$

It is noteworthy that the advanced Green's function $G^a(E)$ is the conjugated transpose of the retarded Green's function. With the broadening functions and Green's functions, it is possible to determine the energy dependent elastic transmission as in Equation 12

$$T(E) = Tr[\Gamma^L G^r(E) \Gamma^R G^a(E)] \quad (12)$$

The transmission is related, through Equation 13, to the conductance through the relation [23]

$$G = G_0 T(E_F) \quad (13)$$

G_0 is the quantum of conductance (with value $7.748 \times 10^{-5} S$).

For the Mach-Zehnder interferometer with direct transmission of light, the state vectors and operators are implemented in agreement with Ref. [24]. Equation 14 describes the photon moving along the x axis as the state vector:

$$x = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

While in Equation 15 the photon moving on the y axis is represented by the state vector:

$$y = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

The two mirrors are represented by the operator M (Equation 16):

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

Equation 17 describes the two beam splitters that are represented by the operator BS :

$$BS = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & i \\ i & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

A 90-degree phase shift is assigned to reflection. The BCPD-based photochromic (BCPD) layer is represented by the operator (Equation 18):

$$BCPD = \begin{bmatrix} \exp\left(i \frac{2\pi d n_{n,c}^{complex}}{\lambda}\right) & 0 \\ 0 & \exp\left(i \frac{2\pi d n_{n,c}^{complex}}{\lambda}\right) \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

With d the thickness of the layer. The thickness of the BCPD layers is 2 μm . This value for the thickness was chosen to obtain a significant phase difference between the BCPD film in the neutral form and BCPD in the charged form.

With the BCPD-based electrochromic layers in the Mach-Zehnder interferometer, the probability to measure the photon with the detectors D1 is given by Equation 19:

$$D1_{BCPD} = |x^T BS M BCPD BSx|^2 \quad (19)$$

While the probability to measure the photon with the detectors D2 is given by Equation 20:

$$D2_{BCPD} = |y^T BS M BCPD BSx|^2 \quad (20)$$

x^T is the transpose of vector x , while y^T is the transpose of vector y .

In the waveguide-based Mach-Zehnder interferometer, the phase shift for two branches with equal length L is given by Equation 21 [13]:

$$\Delta\varphi = \beta_2 L - \beta_1 L \quad (21)$$

In which the parameter β (Equation 22)

$$\beta_{1,2} = \frac{2\pi n_{1,2}}{\lambda} \quad (22)$$

$n_{1,2}$ is the complex refractive index for the materials in the two branches of the Mach-Zehnder interferometer. For this study, $n_1 = n_n^{complex}$ and $n_2 = n_c^{complex}$. The output powers at port 1 and porta 2 (Figure 2b) are given by Equation 23 and 24:

$$P_{out,1} = \sin^2\left(\frac{\Delta\varphi}{2}\right) P_{in,1} + \cos^2\left(\frac{\Delta\varphi}{2}\right) P_{in,2} \quad (23)$$

$$P_{out,2} = \cos^2\left(\frac{\Delta\varphi}{2}\right) P_{in,1} + \sin^2\left(\frac{\Delta\varphi}{2}\right) P_{in,2} \quad (24)$$

Results and discussion

In Figure 1 we show the chemical sketch of the molecule N,N'-bis(cysteine)pyromellitic diimide (BCPD). Carbon (in black), oxygen (in red), and nitrogen (in blue) atoms are indexed as the Hueckel Hamiltonian.

Figure 1. Chemical sketch N,N'-bis(cysteine)pyromellitic diimide (BCPD). The atoms are numbered as in the Hueckel Hamiltonian (the two hydrogen atoms are not numbered).

In fact, in the Hamiltonian of BCPD reported in Equation 25 the diagonal elements correspond to the different atoms of the molecules, while non-null off-diagonal elements correspond to nearest neighbor elements:

$$H = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha N & \beta N & 0 & 0 & \beta N & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \beta N & \alpha & \beta & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta O & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \beta & \alpha & \beta & 0 & \beta & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \beta & \alpha & \beta & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \beta N & 0 & 0 & \beta & \alpha & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta O \\ 0 & 0 & \beta & 0 & 0 & \alpha & \beta & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta & \alpha & \beta & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta & \alpha & \beta & \beta & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta & \alpha & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta & 0 & \alpha & \beta N & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta O & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta N & \alpha N & \beta N & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta N & \alpha & 0 & \beta O & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \beta O & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \alpha O & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta O & 0 & \alpha O & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta O & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \alpha O & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta O & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \alpha O \end{bmatrix} \quad (25)$$

Where the on-site energy α is set to 0 eV and the nearest neighbour element β is set to -3 eV, following the publication of Solomon et al. [22]. Equation 26 reports the other matrix elements:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha N = 0.51\beta \\ \alpha O = 0.97\beta \\ \beta N = 1.02\beta \\ \beta O = 1.02\beta \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

We have studied the complex refractive index of BCPD in the neutral form and with the addition of a charge. We have focused on the wavelength of 800 nm, since it is a wavelength in which there are commercially available single photon sources.

The extinction coefficient k for the neutral BCPD is $k_n = 2.6086 \times 10^{-8}$, while the extinction coefficient k for the charged BCPD is $k_c = 3.3821 \times 10^{-6}$. The real part of the refractive index for the neutral BCPD is $n_n = 1.6393$, while the real part of the refractive index for the charged BCPD is $n_c = 1.4799$.

Figure 2. (a) Sketch of the Mach-Zehnder interferometer, with direct transmission of light, with the photon source, the two mirrors M, the two 50/50 beam splitters BS1 and BS2, the two electrochromic layers BCPDx (along the x direction transmitted by BS1) and BCPDy (along the y direction reflected by BS1), and the two detectors D1 and D2. (b) waveguide-based Mach-Zehnder interferometer with inputs In1 and In2, two 3 dB couplers, and two outputs Out1 and Out2. In one of the branches of the interferometer, the electric field induces a change of the refractive index of BCPD.

We have simulated the Mach-Zehnder interferometer with direct transmission of light, taking into account the 2 micrometer-thick slabs of BCPD. With BCPD in the neutral form in the x axis, and with the BCPD in the charged form in the y-axis (Figure 2a), the probability to detect a photon at detector D1 is 0.4509, while the probability to detect a photon at detector D2 is 0.5491.

We have then simulated the waveguide-based Mach-Zehnder interferometer in a glass slab, with 2 micrometer-long arms. Considering the input power at port 2 equal to zero ($P_{in,2} = 0$, Figure 2b), and considering branches of the interferometer with length $L = 2$ micrometers, the probability to detect a photon at output port 1 is 0.9017, while the probability to detect a photon at output port 2 is 0.0983.

Figure 3. Simulated elastic transmission spectrum, as a function of the energy, of N,N'-bis(cysteine)pyromellitic diimide (BCPD)

Finally, with the nonequilibrium Green's function formalism we have determined the conductance of BCPD. In Figure 3 we show the elastic transmission spectrum (in logarithm scale) of BCPD. Setting the Fermi energy at 0 eV in Equation 13, the conductance of BCPD is 0.127 μ S.

Conclusion

In this work, we have used an electrochromic molecule, N,N'-bis(cysteine)pyromellitic diimide (BCPD), demonstrating that it possesses a refractive index that depends on the applied electric field. Taking advantage of this refractive index control, we have simulated the probability of single-photon detection on a Mach-Zehnder interferometer with direct light transmission and on a waveguide-based Mach-Zehnder interferometer, for example buried in a glass slab. The waveguide-based Mach-Zehnder interferometer can be useful in integrated photonic platforms. We have also studied the conductance of BCPD with the nonequilibrium Green's function formalism. The results of this study could be of interest for quantum communication.

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